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Magic Squares

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Magic Squares

For $n \geq 2$, let A be set of n^2 elements and l an n -ary relation defined on A . As a generalization of the XVIth-XVIIth century magic squares, we present the magic square of order n . This is square array of elements of A arranged so that l applied to all rows and columns yields the same result.

If A is an arithmetic progression and l addition, then many such magic squares are known. The following appeared in Durer's 1514 engraving, "Melancholia"

16	3	2	13
5	10	11	8
9	6	7	12
4	15	14	1

Questions:

1) Can you find magic square of order at least three or four where A is a set of prime numbers and l is addition?

2) Same question when A is a set of square, cube or other spacial numbers such as the Fibonacci, Lucas, triangular or Smarandache quotients. Given any m , the Smarandache Quotient $q(m)$ is the smallest number k such that mk is a factorial.

A similar definition for the magic cube of order n , where the elements of A are arranged in the form of a cube of length n .

3) Study questions similar to those above for the cube. An interesting law may be

$$l(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = a_1 + a_2 - a_3 + a_4 - a_5 \dots$$

References

- [1] F.Smarandache, "Properties of the Numbers", University of Craiova Archives, 1975. [See also the Arizona State Special Collections, Tempe, AZ., USA].